

Artificial intelligence is the magic wand making customer-centric a reality! An investigation into the relationship between consumer purchase intention and consumer engagement through affective attachment

Muhammad Bilal^a, Yunfeng Zhang^{a,*}, Shukai Cai^a, Umair Akram^b, Alrence Halibas^b

^a School of Economics and Management, Anhui Polytechnic University, Wuhu, China

^b The Business School, RMIT University, Ho Chi Minh, Viet Nam

ARTICLE INFO

Handling Editor: Prof. H. Timmermans

Keywords:

Artificial intelligence
Consumer engagement on social media
Consumer experience
Purchase intention

ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence (AI) is revolutionizing consumer-provider interactions by changing the nature of online purchases. This study uses the social support theory to investigate consumer purchase intentions by combining AI technology, consumer social media engagement, and consumer experience. Online surveys are conducted with 467 Chinese social media users who had experience with online purchasing and AI technology. Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) is used to examine the data and proposed hypothesis. This study finds that AI positively affects consumer experience and consumer engagement on social media. Similarly, a positive relationship exists between social media engagement and consumer experience, leading to a more satisfied consumer and amplified purchase intentions. Additionally, affective attachment moderates the relationship between consumer satisfaction and purchase intention. The results reveal that AI can be used on social media to improve consumer experience and increase customer satisfaction levels and purchase intention. We also provide tips for developing flawless service business models. Marketers should explore making social media posts more engaging by using vibrant images and videos to attract customers and prompt them to create, circulate, and share said content on various social media networks.

1. Introduction

The world is undergoing a profound transformation following the advent of artificial intelligence (AI). AI-equipped machines can perform complex tasks, such as problem solving, planning, and learning, by mimicking human intelligence (Overgoor et al., 2019). AI has revolutionized traditional business performance tools (Wen et al., 2022; Crittenden et al., 2019) into modernized sentient machines that exhibit multiple thinking abilities (e.g., self-learning, automatic mental effort, and self-programming) (Kumar et al., 2019).

The development of AI technology has revolutionized various business aspects (e.g., marketing, customer service, and consumer interaction) (Bock et al., 2020) and is gaining popularity worldwide. With the use of AI, problems can be handled in a logical and inventive manner through machine learning. AI is a burning topic amongst marketers and consumers, and it provides benefits to both groups. Kim and Kim (2017) report that many customers have profited from using AI to meet daily

tasks, saving them time and money. AI has enabled inconceivable situations to become feasible and easy to achieve (Weber and Schütte, 2019). AI is making it possible to engage with operations in a user-friendly and consumer-oriented manner. The expectations of today's consumers are centered on convenience and comfort, and AI effectively meets these parameters. Consumers find it easy to use AI to find, choose, buy, and dispose of items. Using AI, consumers can order and evaluate products from anywhere in the world without difficulty (Paschen et al., 2020).

1.1. How companies use AI

Companies use AI in various ways, such as empowering consumers to make informed decisions (Elliott, 2018; Lu et al., 2016), enhancing customer experience, improving business efficiency, promoting continuous harmony and interaction with stakeholders (Butt et al., 2021), and improving customer service processes and product quality (Sarkar et al.,

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: bilal_ashraf30@hotmail.com (M. Bilal), zhangyunfengyj@163.com (Y. Zhang), zhangyunfengyj@163.com (S. Cai), umair.akram@rmit.edu.vn (U. Akram), alrence.halibas@rmit.edu.vn (A. Halibas).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2023.103674>

Received 5 September 2023; Received in revised form 22 November 2023; Accepted 6 December 2023

Available online 15 December 2023

0969-6989/© 2023 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

2020). A company's use of AI can enhance customer experience by finding innovative and long-term solutions and improve company strategy by making complex, critical decisions in unpredictable, competitive, and insecure markets. According to Lee et al. (2022), AI's contribution to the global economy is expected to increase from \$20.82 billion in 2020 to \$15 trillion in 2030. The integration of AI into Web 2.0 marketing applications (Lee et al., 2022) can help firms to meet customers' demands swiftly and become more credible to loyal consumers (Potdar et al., 2018). To manage marketing activities efficiently and maximize consumer engagement on social media (Borges et al., 2021), many companies use AI (e.g., chatbots, recognizing consumer features, and recommending content) (Chiu et al., 2021) to improve customer experience by offering personalized online shopping information and recommending more purchases (Song et al., 2020). Firms use AI-based technologies to acquire, retain, and manage strong consumer relationships across social media (Overgoor et al., 2019).

AI and social media are integrated into e-commerce business operations to build effective consumer relationships (Dwivedi et al., 2019). With these technologies, consumers have a better knowledge of products (Grewal et al., 2017), which can positively affect their purchasing behavior (Thakur, 2018). As a result, companies are now able to achieve top of mind awareness with the consumer (Pantano et al., 2019). A company that uses social media expects satisfied customers to post reviews on its social media pages. These reviews support the business to connect with prospects, influence the attitudes of consumers, raises brand awareness (Moon et al., 2021), and enables consumer feedback (Singh et al., 2020). Moreover, Yang and DeHart, (2016) reports that social media helps improve product quality and service as well as increase revenue and sales. Negative opinions from dissatisfied clients can, however, adversely affect growth, brand image, and performance (Gan, 2017).

1.2. A framework for AI-integrated social media and consumer purchase intentions

Recently, researchers have examined the factors affecting consumer behavior and purchase intentions as a result of the conflicting business scenarios described above (Baabdullah, 2018; Khamis et al., 2016). As consumers spend a considerable amount of time (four to 7 h per day) on social networking sites (Yang et al., 2020), AI can be used to monitor their behavior and understand their purchase patterns (Zhou et al., 2018). An increasing number of firms are applying AI-integrated social media platforms to enhance engagement and competitiveness of their businesses (Sarkar et al., 2020). A few empirical studies have demonstrated that AI-integrated social media can enhance consumer engagement and purchase intentions (Chaouali et al., 2016). To contribute to the literature on AI-based social media, this study examines a framework that integrates several factors influencing consumer purchase intentions. Research shows that social media engagement constantly influences consumer purchase decisions (Yang and DeHart, 2016). Potdar et al. (2018) describe how AI influences consumer behavior by searching for products across various websites to make purchases, which is also becoming an essential element of digital transformation, greatly affecting consumer purchase decisions (Danckwerts and Kenning, 2019). There is, however, not enough evidence that shows how AI affects consumer engagement on social media. This study proposes to add to the literature on this topic by examining the following research questions:

RQ1. Is AI technology useful in the consumer purchase decision making process?

RQ2. Does AI affect consumer social media engagement and purchase intention?

RQ3. Does affective attachment moderate the relationship between consumer satisfaction and purchase intention?

The rest of the study is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews the relevant literature. Section 3 presents related theories and develops the conceptual model. Section 4 presents the research methodology. Section 5 focuses on presenting the data analysis. Section 6 tests the model using a statistical approach. Section 7 discusses and analyzes the results, explores the study's limitations, and outlines theoretical and practical implications.

2. Conceptual background

2.1. Artificial intelligence

AI refers to the ability of computers to perform tasks that need intelligence (e.g., learning, design, serious thinking, and innovative problem solving) (Yin and Qiu, 2021), similar to what humans do (Mogaji et al., 2020). Firms rely on AI to gain a competitive edge through digitalization (Jang et al., 2021). Compared with humans, AI processes information faster, makes better decisions, and does not exhibit bias (Samara et al., 2020). Firms use AI to gather data from multiple sources, including chatbots, location-based advertisements, social media, e-mails, and websites, to create a large volume of digital information, referred to as big data (Yang et al., 2020).

Unsurprisingly, China is one of the top players in AI, not only in terms of technology development, but also in footings of regulation. Currently, China has the most comprehensive set of legislative acts and state plans containing AI technology priorities, but their vagueness and overtly declarative nature hamper their diversity. It is expected that by 2025, China will be the world leader in AI technologies and applications, and will achieve breakthroughs in basic AI theories. The core AI industry is expected to reach 400 billion RMB, whereas the associated AI industry is expected to be worth 5 trillion RMB. By 2025, AI will also be the subject of a new legal framework, including safety assessments, supervision, and standards (State Council of the People's Republic of China, 2017). Consequently, in China, AI is regarded as a new engine of economic development; therefore, AI studies are crucial (Yang et al., 2020) (Table 1).

2.2. Social support theory

Social support is defined as "individuals' perceptions of how others in their social network support them or are supportive of their actions, which may enhance their operative or protect them from harmful outcomes" (Huang et al., 2010). Initially, social support theory (SST) was developed in terms of offline environments and mental health (Cohen and Wills, 1985).

Since computer-mediated communication has gained popularity, various empirical studies have examined online virtual social support using SST. Sharma and Khadka (2019) find that consumers' AI experience, social media engagement, and satisfaction constitute nurturing support, while in online social support groups, both informational and tangible support facilitate actions, providing a sense of empowerment. According to Huang et al. (2010), expressions and instrumental support affect social capital and instant messaging. Leong et al. (2020) find that satisfaction, consumer experience, and social media engagement affect trust in social commerce.

This study examines several aspects of social support (e.g., consumer AI experience, social media engagement, and satisfaction) because they have online social characteristics (Rozzell et al., 2014) that can reveal insights into human-AI interactions. This approach combines multidimensional social support and subsequent interaction behaviors to explain how people engage in it and their satisfaction with it.

2.3. Purchase intention

Customers are more likely to purchase products or services when they are satisfied with their experience. Customers' repeat business is an

Table 1
Summary of earlier research related to AI.

Source	Study focus	Applying Theory	Sampling and location	Methods	Key antecedents and moderator/ Mediator	Dependent variables
Bhagat et al. (2023)	Explore the factors affecting practical implacability of artificial intelligence and its impact on consumers' online purchase intention.		920, India	SEM	Subjective norms, faith, consciousness, affect artificial intelligence	Purchase intention
Zhu et al. (2023)	Investigating customers' responses to artificial intelligence.	Stimulus–Organism–Response (SOR)	566, China	PLS-SEM	Responsiveness, perceived usefulness, Personalization, Information, product familiarity (Moderation)	Trust, Purchase intention
Bag et al. (2022)	Role of digital artificial intelligence (AI) technologies on user engagement and conversion.	SOR	336, India	SEM	Artificial intelligence, digital disruption, user engagement, Behavioral	Repurchase intention
Cheng and Jiang (2022)	To examine Customer–brand relationship in the era of artificial intelligence.		1072, USA	SEM	Brand communication, brand management, artificial intelligence, chatbot marketing efforts, customer–brand relationship (mediator)	Customer response
Sands et al. (2021)	Encounter with a service agent or chatbot.		262, US	Experimental design	Service interaction; emotion; Rapport; service script (moderator)	Purchase intention; experience satisfaction
Yin and Qiu (2021)	Impact of AI Technology and Online Purchase Intention.	SOR	688, China	SEM	Artificial intelligence marketing; online shopping; perceived utility value; perceived hedonic value (mediator)	Consumer Purchase intention
Pillai et al. (2020)	Examine Shopping intention at AI-powered Automated Retail Stores.	TAM	1250, Taiwan	PLS-SEM	Perceived enjoyment, customization, interactivity, artificial intelligence-powered automated retail stores.	Customer Intention to shop
Liang et al. (2020)	To investigate consumers' attitudes and purchase intention toward an AI device.	TAM	313, US	SEM	Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and performance risk were significant in consumers' attitude toward AI, fashion involvement (moderator)	Purchase intention;
Xu et al. (2019)	Neural Network Approach to Predict Customers' Intention to Purchase Battery Electric Vehicles.	Theory of planned behavior	382, China	SEM	Attitude, perceived behavioral control, and subject norm, environmental performance,	Purchase intention;
Leong et al. (2018)	Antecedent's f-commerce and Artificial neural network.	Web Usage Theory, Trust Transference Theory	808, Malaya	ANOVA	hedonic motivation, browsing, age, trust motivation, participation, utilitarian motivation	f-commerce; Actual purchase

important revenue generator for organizations (Alhabash et al., 2015). Online sellers face a particularly challenging task when attempting to understand what motivates consumers to make purchases (Gustad et al., 2018). Additionally, consumers are wary of online purchasing because of such issues as satisfaction, payment procedures, and quality of services (Torres et al., 2019). Despite constant growth over the last two decades (Abidin, 2016), the e-commerce industry remains a minor business. Consumers rely on social media to gather information on their products (Khamis et al., 2016). Businesses use SNS to maximize their conversion rates. Satisfied customers post positive feedback on social media, which influences online communities (Khamis et al., 2016). According to Arora and Narula (2018), engaging with existing consumers is less expensive than appealing to new ones. In this way, firms can attract loyal customers with value-added services, and digital marketing increases the overall return on investment by reducing promotion expenses and increasing return on investment (Wang et al., 2020).

Many people purchase goods and services online. Many business organizations use AI to the fullest extent to provide customers with a better experience and increase their intention to purchase certain products and services. Customers can experience virtual products at their convenience and make decisions by using this service. With AI, consumers can choose from a wide range of options with abundant information available to them, enabling them to choose the most appropriate alternative from a pool of choices with a variety of options. A recent study found that AI technology can be used in augmented reality

applications to help consumers visualize products differently and make the best purchasing decisions possible (Pantano et al., 2019). AI-enabled technologies have been integrated into the latest generation of organizations to offer consumers the finest and utmost tailored solutions (Reinartz et al., 2019). AI uses creative and innovative technologies to help consumers understand their purchase preferences. AI assists customers automatically upon availing of the service. Several studies have suggested that AI aims to create programs that can solve problems in a way that is parallel to humans and enhance decision-making abilities regarding purchase intention (Liu et al., 2019; Hasan et al., 2021; Flavián et al., 2022). AI is relevant and successful, because it provides consumers with a bulky amount of relevant, structured, and high-quality information on purchase-related actions (Sohn and Kwon, 2020). AI-enabled online stores are more successful in attracting customers after they make purchases.

3. Hypothesis development

3.1. AI and consumer experience

Consumer experience describes how customers interact with and feel about a company or brand based on their interactions and reactions (Samara et al., 2020). A consumer's experience comprises a combination of cognitive, sensory, emotional, and physical elements (Potdar et al., 2018). The cognitive element consists of higher-level mental functions,

including abstract thinking, perception, language, memory, and problem solving (American Psychological Association, 2016). Hsiao and Chen (2016) define the cognitive elements of customer experience as functionality, swiftness, and accessibility. Potdar et al. (2018) highlight the complex emotional aspects of customer service. These feelings may be positive or negative, and may include pleasure, regret, irritation, outrage, and wonder (Hsiao and Chen, 2016).

Customers' physical and sensory experiences differ between online and offline contexts. Offline experiences consider artifacts, lighting, signage, and layout (Torres et al., 2019), whereas online experiences consider easier-to-navigate interfaces and more apparent designs (Hsiao and Chen, 2016). Finally, social elements, such as family and friends, relate to other people's influence on customer experience (Kao et al., 2016). These technologies can enhance a customer's experience only if their preferences and previous experiences are well understood. AI tools can accelerate this process using data and customer profiles to determine the best way to communicate with consumers. Thus, we propose the following hypothesis.

H1. *AI positively influences consumer experience.*

3.2. AI and consumer engagement on social media

AI has a substantial impact on consumer behavior. Companies that use AI may deliver consumers a more tailored shopping experience on social media sites (Sarkar et al., 2020). AI allows these firms to determine the impact of their online marketing strategies by anticipating consumer behavior (Samara et al., 2020) and engaging consumers on social media to create further analytical choices (Jang et al., 2021). For instance, AI turns online shopping into a better experience by gathering and considering product information (Liu et al., 2018) and bridging the gap between companies and consumers. Various issues related to social media can be addressed using AI. For example, employees in the sales department may feel overwhelmed when analyzing large amounts of data provided by social media (Thakur, 2018). The use of AI may provide solutions to such issues in companies (Chaouali et al., 2016), including predictive marketing analytics and automated information mining (Potdar et al., 2018).

According to SST (Mehrabian and Russell, 1974), an individual's response to the external environment is influenced by their psychological and behavioral responses (Pandita et al., 2021). Thus, AI may lead to increased customer engagement on social media. For instance, if companies provide customers with a variety of ways to compare product and service features, AI integration could increase their engagement on social media platforms (Zhou et al., 2018). Based on previous arguments and SST, this study hypothesizes as follows.

H2. *AI positively influences consumer engagement on social media.*

3.3. Consumer experience and satisfaction

A customer's experience is the overall impression of a brand or product after interacting with and learning about it through interactions with it (Samara et al., 2020). There may be a positive or negative reaction to a user's experience depending on their interactions with a product, company, or department within the company (Yang, 2016). In summary, customer experience refers to consumers' internal and subjective reactions to direct or indirect interactions with a firm or brand (Mogaji et al., 2020). Customers expect seamless transactions to save time and effort. The smoothness of a platform improves the level of consumer satisfaction (Yang et al., 2020). According to Sharma and Singh (2016), consumers are satisfied with products when they are pleased with them.

In recent years, there has been an increase in computer-human interaction (Baabdullah, 2018), which has prompted a great deal of research on older technology adoption (Satti et al., 2020). In AI, user experience is highly personal and requires participation at many levels,

including rational, spiritual, sensory, physical, and emotional (Borges et al., 2021). As Rozzell et al. (2014) identified, interacting with AI-enabled tools involves four factors: cognitive, emotional, physical, and social. It has been shown that customers are more likely to be satisfied when they have a memorable and optimistic experience (Hicks et al., 2012). The literature has established a positive correlation between AI customer satisfaction and experience (Loureiro et al., 2017; Hicks et al., 2012). Consequently, AI technologies provide users with a better experience and enhance their confidence, satisfaction, and understanding (Kao et al., 2016). Thus, we propose the following hypothesis.

H3. *AI consumer experience positively influences consumer satisfaction.*

3.4. Consumer engagement on social media and consumer satisfaction

Consumer engagement is an indicator of a firm's commitment to its customers, its ability to maintain customer trust, and the importance of customer loyalty (Nadeem et al., 2021). Consumers of these companies are more likely to share positive experiences of a specific brand with others (Loureiro et al., 2017; Bilal et al., 2020). Customer satisfaction may be higher for those who use social media more often (Majeed et al., 2022). Similarly, Choi and Kandampully (2019) argue that human interactions influence others' psychological processes by influencing their experiences. Satisfaction is a cognitive factor for both consumers and brands. The interaction between the consumer and company may lead consumers to evaluate the product or service confidently (Rather, 2021). Therefore, it is reasonable to assume the following hypothesis.

H4. *AI positively influences consumer engagement and consumer satisfaction.*

3.5. Consumer satisfaction and purchase intention

To retain customers, businesses must deliver high-quality products and offer attractive promotions (Arora and Narula, 2018). Furthermore, product quality, delivery timing, and post-purchase support affect customer satisfaction with digital purchasing (Hsiao and Chen, 2016). Finn (2012) suggests that consumers might purchase from a website when they perceive it as offering a value-added service. To boost customer purchase intentions, marketers must focus on the intrinsic attributes of their websites (Lin and Lekhawipat, 2014). Studies have found that customer satisfaction predicts customer purchase intention (Tan et al., 2013). Customer purchase intention indicates whether consumers intend to purchase a similar product in the upcoming (Kao et al., 2016). Therefore, we assume that satisfied customers will purchase a product (Torres et al., 2019), whereas dissatisfied customers will buy the product or service from a rival (Borges et al., 2021; Satti et al., 2020). Therefore, it is logical to propose the following hypothesis.

H5. *Consumer satisfaction positively influences purchase intention.*

3.6. The moderating role of affective attachment

The term "affective attachment" refers to the emotional bond a person has with a particular object (Jamieson et al., 2000), brand (Rioux et al., 2017), or location (Yuksel et al., 2010). Rioux et al. (2017) define affective attachment as building and strengthening relationships. From this perspective, affective attachment promotes emotional links and indulgence, causing individuals to be more willing to care for one another. In addition to conveying deep identification with the individual in focus, affective attachment expresses long-term reciprocal exchange (Hsiao and Chen, 2016). This study defines an individual's emotional bond with AI as affective attachment. According to Hicks et al. (2012), satisfaction is an underlying factor in affective attachment. A positive brand experience strengthens brand affinity, which in turn affects brand satisfaction (Rioux et al., 2017). If users have a good experience with AI,

their attachment to it increases.

Affective attachment can play a role in online purchase intention, as it involves feelings of trust and security, which are important in any type of relationship. In e-commerce, affective attachment refers to a consumer's emotional connection with a particular brand, website, or seller (Hsiao and Chen, 2016). Wang et al. (2020) find that consumers who felt comfortable and confident purchasing from a particular online store or brand were likelier to do so in the future.

However, if consumers have a negative affective attachment to a particular online store or brand, they may be less likely to make purchases from that seller, because they might not feel confident or comfortable with the transaction (Yang et al., 2020). Therefore, building and maintaining a positive affective attachment with customers is essential for online businesses. Brand image can be supported by offering a personal experience, providing excellent customer service, and maintaining a consistent and trustworthy image. By doing so, businesses can increase customer loyalty and boost online purchase intention. Therefore, it is logical to hypothesize as follows.

H6. *Affective attachment moderates the relationship between consumer satisfaction and purchase intention.*

4. Research methodology

4.1. Sampling and data collection

A questionnaire was distributed online via a social network application, namely, WeChat, to assess the reliability of the measurement scales. WeChat is China's most popular social media platform, with approximately 1.2 billion active users. Its Moments feature (similar to Instagram) makes it particularly popular. Social commerce on WeChat has evolved rapidly and become extremely important in China, making the country a prime location for exploring online consumer shopping in social commerce. Thus, WeChat users were chosen as the research subjects.

The data were obtained between November 2022 and February 2023. The questionnaire was initially distributed in four large first-tier Chinese cities (Beijing, Tianjin, Shanghai, and Guangzhou). These cities were surveyed for two reasons: (1) these cities are financial and commercial hubs in China and a large number of social media savvy consumers reside there; and (2) social media users aged between 18 and 40 years find it more convenient and have better infrastructure than older users. Beijing, Tianjin, Shanghai, and Guangzhou collectively have large populations of young consumers in our target market, who also reflect Chinese influencers' behavior.

A purposive sampling method was used to locate relevant respondents. For an unknown population, Hair et al. (2014) recommend a scale with 5–10 times the number of items. Our questionnaire included 30 items. To conduct this research, we required 125–500 respondents. The smallest sample size was resolved using the G*Power statistical test and general rule of thumb. Based on a medium effect size f^2 of 0.15, 0.05 (Alpha) error probability, 0.8 power, and five predictors, 92 respondents is the minimum sample size. In total, 497 valid responses were obtained. Power values of 0.998 were obtained when a post-hoc test was conducted with 467 samples. Our respondents were social media influencers with 1000 to 10,000 followers each. All respondents were required to prove that they were users of AI and had to certify that they were social media users. Initially, we searched for people who used social media and met other conditions.

4.2. Respondent profile

The research questionnaire had two sections. Part A detailed the demographic profile of respondents, revealing that 62.7% were male and 37.3% female; furthermore, 46.3% of the respondents held a bachelor's grade, and the majority (46.9%) were aged between 20 and

30 years. Part B of the questionnaire studied the frequency of online purchases (Table 2).

4.3. Ethical permission

In preparation for participating in the study, invited respondents were informed that their names and e-mail addresses would remain confidential. In addition, participation was voluntary, and no gift or money was offered in exchange for completion of the survey.

4.4. Measures

This study used a variety of measurement scales: an eight-item AI scale from Capatina et al. (2020); a three-item AI consumer experience scale from Agarwal and Singh (2018); a modified five-item consumer engagement on social media scale from Habibi et al. (2014) and Laroche et al. (2012); a three-item affective attachment scale based on Yuksel et al. (2010); a four-item purchase intention scale based on Davis, (1989); and a four-item consumer satisfaction scale based on Oghuma et al. (2016). We developed an online questionnaire in English to evaluate these constructs. To measure the construct, we used a five-point Likert scale ranging from "strongly disagree" (1) to "strongly agree" (5). As our target audience was Chinese social media influencers, our questionnaire was translated into standard Chinese (Mandarin) to improve its accuracy (Brislin, 1970). The reliability of our measurement scales was assessed with 30 respondents before we finalized our questionnaire. Table 3 shows the reliability of each measurement scale used in this study.

4.5. Missing value treatment

The possibility of missing data in multivariate analyses is common in sample surveys (Little, 1988, p. 287). Social science researchers, such as those studying marketing, hospitality, tourism, and information systems, continue to face challenges in addressing missing values. According to Schafer and Olsen (1998) and Rezaei and Ghodsi (2014), multiple imputations are the most effective and reliable solutions for missing values. According to Schafer and Olsen (1998), multiple imputation is a simulation technique that provides complete data for each missing observation and a set of plausible values for each observation (Rubin, 1987). This study applied the expectation-maximization algorithm (EMA) (Little, 1988) in SPSS software to impute and handle missing values efficiently. A slightly missing completely at random (MCAR) X^2 statistic was achieved, and it was discovered that the missing

Table 2
Respondent information.

Measure	Item	Frequency	%
Gender	Male	293	62.7
	Female	174	37.3
	Total	467	100
Age (years)	Less than 20	21	4.5
	20–30	219	46.9
	31–40	120	25.7
	41–50	81	17.3
	above 50	26	5.6
	Total	467	100
Education	High school or below	32	6.8
	College certificate	73	15.6
	Bachelor's degree	216	46.3
	Master's degree	119	25.5
	Doctoral Degree	27	5.8
	Total	467	100
Frequency of online purchase	Everyday	90	19.3
	Always	191	40.9
	Sometime	115	24.6
	Seldom	71	15.2
	Total	467	100

Table 3
Measurement properties.

Construct	Loading factor (L.F.)	t-value	α	CR	VIF
Artificial Intelligence			0.72	0.84	3.7
AI 1	0.82	31.09			
AI 2	0.85	28.47			
AI 3	0.81	33.57			
AI 4	0.91	39.21			
AI 5	0.89	25.71			
AI 6	0.83	33.24			
AI 7	0.91	36.21			
AI 8	0.84	35.31			
Consumer Satisfaction			0.78	0.87	3.9
CS 1	0.89	37.32			
CS 2	0.91	35.51			
CS 3	0.96	33.15			
CS 4	0.87	39.13			
Consumer Experience			0.73	0.83	3.5
CE 1	0.87	29.24			
CE 2	0.91	32.15			
CE 3	0.95	36.43			
Consumer Engagement on Social Media			0.82	0.86	3.6
CESM 1	0.99	31.21			
CESM 2	0.89	37.15			
CESM 3	0.92	39.32			
CESM 4	0.89	35.14			
CESM 5	0.91	34.12			
Affective Attachment			0.76	0.88	3.8
AFA 1	0.92	38.49			
AFA 2	0.80	33.31			
AFA 3	0.89	39.51			
Purchase intention			0.79	0.89	3.9
PI 1	0.81	32.41			
PI 2	0.94	35.13			
PI 3	0.95	33.42			
PI 4	0.88	38.51			

data were at random (Little’s MCAR test: $X^2 = 331.339$, $df = 327$, significance = 0.429). In this manner, missing values were imputed using EMA (Akram et al., 2017).

4.6. Common method bias

Common method bias (CMB) can be used in behavioral research (Podsakoff et al., 2003). The results obtained from this type of research are likely to be compromised by the noise of biased instruments (Chang et al., 2010). This study evaluated the structural relationships between the independent and dependent variables using a latent variable approach. Behavioral research commonly uses Harman’s one-factor test to determine the presence of CMB (Podsakoff et al., 2003). Ideally, a single factor should have variance of less than 50%. The maximum proportion of variance illustrated by a single factor was 38.1%.

5. Data analysis and results

We used partial least squares (PLS) structural equation modeling (SEM) to analyze the data. It is well established that PLS-SEM is widely used in the field of social science, particularly marketing (Upadhyay and Kamble, 2023; Chatterjee et al., 2022). PLS defines weight dealings that are used for the estimation of latent variable case values, which are not offered by other SEM methods, in which independent variables are used to explain as much variance in the dependent variables as possible. This method was adopted because it does not impose any restrictions on the sample size (Chekima et al., 2016). PLS-SEM can perform multivariate analysis without requiring a normal distribution (De Silva et al., 2021). The PLS-SEM technique does not require a normal distribution for multivariate analysis, which is necessary for the Covariance-Based Structural Equation Modeling (CB-SEM) technique (De Silva et al., 2021). An exploratory study using PLS-SEM technique will almost

certainly yield better results (Chen and Tung, 2014). Researchers can also use PLS to measure heterogeneity in path modeling through its methodological approach. Chin (2010) and Henseler and Chin (2010) recommend the use of a two-stage approach. First, the measurement model was assessed, and then the structural model was evaluated in accordance with previous studies (Rezaei, 2015). Thus, PLS-SEM was used to empirically verify the suggested model (Fig. 1), measurement, and structural model using the Smart-PLS software (Ringle et al., 2005). A survey was conducted using this method, and answers were calculated. After reviewing the quantified feedback from the respondents, we proceed to step two.

5.1. Assessment measurement model

The loading factor (LF) of each item was calculated to confirm the instrument’s reliability and convergent validity and to illustrate the associated constructs. Considering the items corresponding to each construct, we calculated the average variance extracted (AVE), Cronbach’s alpha (α), and composite reliability (CR); for each construct, reliability, consistency, and validity were determined. We calculated the variance inflation factor (VIF) for each construct to determine whether multicollinearity defects (Bisbe et al., 2007). The t-values of each item for each country were computed to verify the consistency of the loadings. The results are summarized in Table 3.

All parameters of the results are in the ranges that are specified in the results because, according to Latan and Noonan (2017), the final acceptable value of LF is 0.707, and AVE is acceptable at a minimum of 0.5 (Agrawal et al., 2015), and Cronbach’s alpha is acceptable at 0.6, and the value of CR is 0.7 (Hair et al., 2012). The results suggest that the expected VIF values are in the range of 3.3 (Ahmad et al., 2021). The identified instruments and constructs showed high reliability, consistency, and validity. These constructs did not exhibit multicollinearity.

Our research team identified the items that correlated with the constructs. We ensured that each item was approved by the discriminant test. This test aims to determine whether each instrument and its construct can fully clarify the construct and whether the instruments interpret other constructs. The analysis could be compromised if this is not ensured, as this could lead to errors. Therefore, we conducted discriminant validity tests. The AVE square roots are more significant than the correlation coefficients of the constructs with other constructs matching the AVE square roots (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). This condition must be satisfied for the discriminant validity test. All AVE square roots are presented diagonally, whereas the correlation coefficients are presented off-diagonally (see Table 4a).

In addition, Heterotrait–Monotrait (HTMT) ratios are commonly used to assess discriminant validity (Sarstedt et al., 2021). All our HTMT values were below the recommended value of 0.90 (Henseler et al., 2015); in this way, discriminant validity was demonstrated (see Table 4b).

5.2. Structural model

By performing PLS analysis on our research model, we validated hypothesized relationships. All hypotheses were supported after statistical validation. After validation, Fig. 2 shows the conceptual models. The impact of AI on CE and CESM is concerning. It seems that the effect of AI on CE (H1) is higher; it is significant that the pat coefficient was 0.76, with the significant level ** ($p < 0.01$). Regarding the effect of CE and CESM on ST, the impact of CE on ST is higher, with a pat coefficient of 0.65 and a significant value * ($p < 0.05$). When viewing the effect of ST on PI, we found that the ST on PI with the significant value *** ($p < 0.001$) and path coefficient is 0.67. As a result, the moderation analysis views that AFA significantly influences the linkage between H6 (ST → PI). In terms of the coefficient determinant (R^2), CE can explain 73% ($R^2 = 0.73$) of AI, and CESM can explain 69% ($R^2 = 0.69$). ST can clarify CE and CESM up to 77% ($R^2 = 0.77$). The PI can be ready by ST up to 81% ($R^2 = 0.81$).

Fig. 1. Research framework.

Table 4a
Discriminant validity: (Fornell and Larcker criterion).

Constructs	AI	CE	CESM	ST	AFA	PI	SD	Mean	AVE
AI	0.80						1.33	3.46	0.65
CE	0.39	0.83					1.41	3.42	0.69
CESM	0.41	0.49	0.84				1.66	4.29	0.71
ST	0.33	0.41	0.47	0.82			1.47	4.59	0.68
AFA	0.44	0.39	0.54	0.61	0.85		1.53	3.99	0.73
PI	0.31	0.33	0.92	0.49	0.41	0.87	1.49	3.25	0.76

NOTE: AI = Artificial intelligence, CE = Consumer experience, CESM – Consumer engagement social media, ST = Satisfaction, AFA = Affective attachment, PI = Purchase intention. Diagonal values (bold) show the square root of the AVE. *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01; ***p < 0.001.

Table 4b
Discriminant validity (HTMT).

Key variables	AI	CE	CESM	ST	AFA	PI
AI	-					
CE	0.64	-				
CESM	0.59	0.53	-			
ST	0.69	0.64	0.71	-		
AFA	0.61	0.49	0.68	0.75	-	
PI	0.67	0.61	0.62	0.63	0.59	-

NOTE: AI = Artificial intelligence, CE = Consumer experience, CESM = Consumer engagement social media, ST = Satisfaction, AFA = Affective attachment. PI = Purchase intention. *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01; ***p < 0.001.

= 0.81). The model had an 81 % explanatory power. Table 5, and Table 6 provide the results of the proposed hypotheses (see Fig. 3).

6. Discussion

This study investigates how AI technology can influence consumer behavior, especially purchase intention, through social media marketing. Our study uses SST to explain how firms use AI in their social media marketing campaigns to stimulate customer responses. This study indicates that firms that use AI in their social media marketing campaigns increase consumer satisfaction and engagement. Companies can use modern AI-based tools to expand social media drives relevant to customers. Furthermore, companies can use AI technology to convert

traditional businesses into digital businesses by attracting website traffic through social media marketing campaigns, which are then converted into customers to remain competitive (Zhou et al., 2018). Firms' use of AI in social media promotions contributes to an increase in sales volume owing to the positive link between AI and consumer experience (Loureiro et al., 2017).

In this study, AI was positively associated with consumer engagement in social media (Hsiao and Chen, 2016). These findings support the idea that marketers can engage potential consumers by integrating AI into social media (Abidin, 2016). Furthermore, Khamis et al. (2016) find a positive correlation between social media engagement and customer satisfaction, and thus, more engaged customers were more likely to be satisfied. The results of this study confirm previous research, showing that customers are more likely to give positive ratings to products on social media platforms when they are satisfied with the product (Loureiro et al., 2017).

Consequently, the social media literature indicates that AI-based digital technologies, including virtual and augmented reality, are capable of enhancing consumer engagement and converting them into consumers (Gan, 2017). Additionally, the findings of this study suggest that AI can support chatbots and virtual assistants (Yang et al., 2020), and that their combination with social media may enhance consumer satisfaction. This study found empirical evidence that customer purchase intention is positively influenced by customer engagement on social media (Zhou et al., 2018; Mogaji et al., 2020).

COVID-19 has changed consumers' buying behavior, and they are

Fig. 2. After validation.

Fig. 3. Moderating plot of affective attachment.

Table 5
Coefficient, R², p-values.

Path	Hypothesis	R ² /path coefficient	p-value	Hypothesis Supported
Effects on CE				
By AI.	H1	0.76	** (p < 0.01)	Yes
Effect on CESH				
By AI.	H2	0.63	*** (p < 0.001)	Yes
Effects on ST				
By CE.	H3	0.65	* (p < 0.05)	Yes
By CESH	H4	0.59	** (p < 0.01)	Yes
Effects on PI				
By ST.	H5	0.67	*** (p < 0.001)	Yes

Notes: ***p < 0.001; **p < 0.01; *p < 0.05.

now more willing to buy products online without interacting with a seller (Zhu et al., 2022). This illustrates that social media can improve consumer engagement and purchase opportunities (Song et al., 2020). Additionally, the current research shows that consumer experience and satisfaction positively influence purchase intentions. Based on past

Table 6
Path weight, hypothesis, p-value with moderation.

Path	Hypothesis	Path Coefficient	p-value	Hypothesis Supported
AI → CE	H1	0.42	** (p < 0.01)	Yes
AI → CESH	H2	0.39	* (p < 0.05)	Yes
CE → ST	H3	0.37	** (p < 0.01)	Yes
CESH → ST	H4	0.43	*** (p < 0.001)	Yes
ST → PI	H5	0.41	** (p < 0.01)	Yes
(ST → PI) * AFA	H6	0.36	* (p < 0.05)	Yes

Notes: ***p < 0.001; **p < 0.01; *p < 0.05.

studies (Torres et al., 2019), this study found that online customers prefer to purchase products rated and reviewed by other consumers on social media.

The study also demonstrates that customers' affective attachment moderates its positive connection with satisfaction and purchase intentions. This is consistent with the results of Satti et al. (2020), who demonstrate that customers' affective attachment has ample influence on their purchase intentions, particularly when they are satisfied with their consumer experience. Therefore, building and maintaining a positive affective attachment with customers is important for online

businesses. This can be attained through various means such as offering personalized experiences, providing excellent customer service, and maintaining a consistent and trustworthy brand image. By doing so, businesses can increase customer loyalty and boost online purchase intention.

6.1. Theoretical contributions

This study makes several significant theoretical contributions to literature. First, to obtain a corresponding research, this study developed a research model of AI technology stimuli, customer experiences, and consumer engagement on social media, leading to purchase intention using SST, followed by interdisciplinary research spanning online consumer behavior. Important theoretical invention and exploration takes place here.

Second, to improve customer engagement on social media, businesses can use AI-enabled systems to determine which product features are important. Owing to the increased use of social media platforms, consumer engagement has been significantly amplified (Chaouali et al., 2016; Bilal et al., 2023; Akram et al., 2021, 2023a), indicating that social media is evolving as a novel space to connect and engage with consumers for the upgrade of goods and services (Abidin, 2016; Akram et al., 2023b). Social media platforms have been monitored and analyzed using AI (Potdar et al., 2018). The COVID-19 pandemic led to increased customer engagement with technology (Zhu et al., 2022). It is necessary to consider AI technology and customer behavior when planning customer engagement strategies to enhance customer purchase intentions. This study recommends that AI technologies make social media platforms more effective in engaging new customers in an organization (Torres et al., 2019).

Third, consumer experience and satisfaction positively affect purchase intentions. Customer experience after a purchase is considered a vital factor affecting customers' decision-making (Su et al., 2016). Furthermore, consumers' satisfaction with their previous purchase experiences determines their loyalty (Hsiao and Chen, 2016). Organizations must utilize digital platforms (Arora and Narula, 2018) to collect customer feedback, effectively manage digital marketing, and use AI technologies (Loureiro et al., 2017). Our research reveals that customers are likely to purchase products from a similar brand if they have a pleasant experience.

Fourth, by exploring the moderating role of affective attachment in the relationship between satisfaction and purchase intention, our findings suggest that customers with high attachment rankings are more likely to purchase. The influence of satisfaction on purchase intention is stronger when online shopping increases; even though customers are satisfied with their buying experience, it may not lead to purchase intention if there is no consumer attachment to the shopping experience.

Finally, this study sheds light on social support theory. As technology-mediated interactions have become more prevalent, numerous empirical investigations have employed SST to analyze online social support. Studies have examined smartphone-based alcoholism forums (Samara et al., 2020), e-commerce sites (Satti et al., 2020), microblogging applications (Bilal et al., 2021), online educational institutions (Chung and Chen, 2018), and Moodle-exploring environments (Paschen et al., 2020). Despite this, little research has been conducted on human-AI interactions through social support. Therefore, our research provides insight into social support via human-AI interactions.

6.2. Practical implications

This study has several implications for both scholars and practitioners. First, in China, customers' social media use has significantly increased after COVID-19. Today, many consumers choose to buy products through social media. Digital platforms and social media can increase business turnover. Companies can easily track customer behavior on social media websites (Loureiro et al., 2017), allowing them

to improve customer satisfaction through effective communication policies.

Second, businesses must engage directly with customers to ascertain their needs and expectations (Thakur, 2018). Consumer satisfaction, rather than social media engagement, is crucial for businesses to thrive. Through our findings, managers should be able to better understand the behavioral and social impacts of disruptive technologies (Baabdullah, 2018).

Third, incorporating social media can help analyze customer responses and convert them into actual customer reactions (Khamis et al., 2016). Firms can predict customers' behavioral trends using AI-enabled social media (Grewal et al., 2017). This framework proposes a method for managers to increase sales volumes by inducing consumers on social media. The study findings can inspire managers to optimize social media interactions by exploiting the latest digital technologies.

Fourth, AI can help businesses increase sales and create digital systems to estimate and examine their social media journeys. Using social media to sell products globally is an effective marketing strategy. This study revealed that frequent online shoppers change their decision patterns after becoming attached to online shopping (Dwivedi et al., 2019). Thus, marketing managers should implement AI to drive customer engagement on social sites.

Furthermore, this study recommends that e-commerce firms use AI-enabled technology to increase consumers' awareness of their online stores and encourage them to buy from them. Our results indicate that consumers feel more inclined to make purchases on online platforms that use AI-enabled technologies, which simplify their purchase decisions. This study supports the idea that e-retailers should use AI-based technology to satisfy customers' purchase intentions. Based on the comments from the respondents and data analysis, the study indicates that e-retailers should apply modern AI technology to gain a competitive advantage over their rivals. These findings confirm that AI is essential for satisfying online consumer purchase intentions. This study established a generic framework for AI-enabled ease of use, and e-retailing firms can use it to boost consumer purchasing intention.

6.3. Limitations and future research directions

This study has some limitations. First, the sample size was small relative to the population. If a larger sample had been used, the conclusions would have been more consistent. More advanced survey methods, such as big data research are recommended for comprehensive and accurate future studies. Second, because humans and robots are perceived as similar, users are less likely to accept human social robots than invisible ones (Mogaji et al., 2020). Therefore, it would be worthwhile to investigate the appearance of AI chatbots (e.g., humanoid or machine-like chatbots) to determine whether a human-like presence leads to greater adoption. Third, the study was conducted during the unprecedented time of the COVID-19 pandemic, and social media influencers may have behaved differently during this period. Social media influencers should be studied in the aftermath of the pandemic to investigate their behavioral intentions and how they relate to AI. Finally, to generalize the findings of this study, researchers could conduct a cross-cultural study that compares consumer behaviors across countries and industries.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Muhammad Bilal: Writing – original draft. **Yunfeng Zhang:** Methodology, Supervision. **Shukai Cai:** Writing – review & editing. **Umair Akram:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Alrence Halibas:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Software.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare there is no conflict of interest.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. 72071002), the Program of Philosophy and Social Science Foundation of Anhui Province, China (AHSKY2022D113), the Program of Social Science Innovation Development of Anhui Province, China (2022CX099), National Social Science Foundation (22BJL064), 2022 Anhui Province University Discipline (Major) Top Talent Academic Support Project (gxbjZD20220222), and Postdoctoral Research Fund of China (No. S022023004).

References

- Abidin, C., 2016. Visibility labour: engaging with Influencers' fashion brands and #OOTD advertorial campaigns on Instagram. *Media Int. Aust.* 161 (1), 86–100.
- Agarwal, A., Singh, M.R., 2018. The relationship between retail experience, customer satisfaction, and behavioral intentions: exploring the consumer shopping behavior in unorganized retail settings. *Indian J. Market.* 48 (1), 9–27.
- Agrawal, V.V., Atasu, A., Van Ittersum, K., 2015. Remanufacturing, third-party competition, and consumers' perceived value of new products. *Manag. Sci.* 61 (1), 60–72.
- Akram, U., Hui, P., Khan, M.K., Saduzai, S.K., Akram, Z., Bhati, M.H., 2017. The plight of humanity: online impulse shopping in China. *Hum. Syst. Manag.* 36 (1), 73–90.
- Ahmad, W., Kim, W.G., Choi, H.M., Haq, J.U., 2021. Modeling behavioral intention to use travel reservation apps: a cross-cultural examination between US and China. *J. Retailing Consum. Serv.* 63, 102689.
- Alhabash, S., McAlister, A.R., Lou, C., Hagerstrom, A., 2015. From clicks to behaviors: the mediating effect of intentions to like, share, and comment on the relationship between message evaluations and offline behavioral intentions. *J. Interact. Advert.* 15 (2), 82–96.
- Akram, U., Lavuri, R., Ansari, A.R., Parida, R., Junaid, M., 2023a. Havocs of social media fake news! Analysing the effect of credibility, trustworthiness, and self-efficacy on consumer's buying intentions. *J. Strat. Market.* 1–15.
- Akram, U., Ansari, A.R., Yan, C., 2023b. Cosmetics makers have always sold 'hope in a jar'! Understanding the cosmetics purchase intention in the Chinese mobile commerce environment. *J. Retailing Consum. Serv.* 73, 103337.
- American Psychological Association, 2016. Guidelines for the undergraduate psychology major: version 2.0. *Am. Psychol.* 71 (2), 102–111.
- Arora, P., Narula, S., 2018. Linkages between service quality, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty: a literature review. *J. Market. Manag.* 17 (4), 30–53.
- Baabdullah, A.M., 2018. Consumer adoption of Mobile Social Network Games (M-SNGs) in Saudi Arabia: the role of social influence, hedonic motivation and trust. *Technol. Soc.* 53, 91–102.
- Bilal, M., Zhang, Y., Cai, S., Akram, U., Luu, N.T.M., 2023. Unlocking luxury purchase intentions in China: a study of consumer attitude, perceived value, and the moderating effect of perceived enjoyment. *Acta Psychol.* 240, 104048.
- Bag, S., Srivastava, G., Bashir, M.M.A., Kumari, S., Giannakis, M., Chowdhury, A.H., 2022. Journey of customers in this digital era: understanding the role of artificial intelligence technologies in user engagement and conversion. *Benchmark Int. J.* 29 (7), 2074–2098.
- Bhagat, R., Chauhan, V., Bhagat, P., 2023. Investigating the impact of artificial intelligence on consumer's purchase intention in e-retailing. *Foresight* 25 (2), 249–263.
- Bilal, M., Jianqiu, Z., Akram, U., Tanveer, Y., Sardar, T., Rasool, H., 2020. Understanding the effects of Internet usage behavior on eWOM. *Int. J. Inf. Syst. Serv. Sect. (IJISSS)* 12 (3), 93–113.
- Bilal, M., Jianqiu, Z., Dukhaykh, S., Fan, M., Trunk, A., 2021. Understanding the effects of eWOM antecedents on online purchase intention in China. *Information* 12 (5), 192.
- Bisbe, J., Batista-Foguet, J.M., Chenhall, R., 2007. Defining management accounting constructs: a methodological note on the risks of conceptual misspecification. *Account. Org. Soc.* 32 (7–8), 789–820.
- Bock, D.E., Wolter, J.S., Ferrell, O.C., 2020. Artificial intelligence: disrupting what we know about services. *J. Serv. Market.* 34 (3), 317–334.
- Borges, A.F., Laurindo, F.J., Spínola, M.M., Gonçalves, R.F., Mattos, C.A., 2021. The strategic use of artificial intelligence in the digital era: systematic literature review and future research directions. *Int. J. Inf. Manag.* 57, 102225.
- Brislin, R.W., 1970. Back-translation for cross-cultural research. *J. Cross Cult. Psychol.* 1 (3), 185–216.
- Butt, A., Ahmad, H., Muzaffar, A., Ali, F., Shafique, N., 2021. WOW, the make-up AR app is impressive: a comparative study between China and South Korea. *J. Serv. Market.* 36 (1), 73–88.
- Capatina, A., Kachour, M., Lichy, J., Micu, A., Micu, A.E., Codignola, F., 2020. Matching the future capabilities of an artificial intelligence-based software for social media marketing with potential users' expectations. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Change* 151, 119794.
- Chang, C., Zhang, L., Zhou, J., Zhang, L., Kennedy, J.F., 2010. Structure and properties of hydrogels prepared from cellulose in NaOH/urea aqueous solutions. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 82 (1), 122–127.
- Chaouali, W., Yahia, I.B., Souiden, N., 2016. The interplay of counter-conformity motivation, social influence, and trust in customers' intention to adopt internet banking services: the case of an emerging country. *J. Retailing Consum. Serv.* 28, 209–218.
- Chatterjee, S., Chaudhuri, R., Vrontis, D., Thrassou, A., 2022. The influence of online customer reviews on customers' purchase intentions: a cross-cultural study from India and the UK. *Int. J. Organ. Anal.* 30 (6), 1595–1623.
- Chekima, B., Wafa, S.A.W.S.K., Igau, O.A., Chekima, S., Sondoh Jr., S.L., 2016. Examining green consumerism motivational drivers: does premium price and demographics matter to green purchasing? *J. Clean. Prod.* 112, 3436–3450.
- Chen, M., Tung, P., 2014. Developing an extended Theory of Planned Behavior model to predict consumers' intention to visit green hotels. *Int. J. Hospit. Manag.* 36, 221–230.
- Cheng, Y., Jiang, H., 2022. Customer-brand relationship in the era of artificial intelligence: understanding the role of chatbot marketing efforts. *J. Prod. Brand Manag.* 31 (2), 252–264.
- Chin, W.W., 2010. How to write up and report pls analyses. In: Esposito Vinzi, V., Chin, W.W., Henseler, J., Wang, H. (Eds.), *Handbook of Partial Least Squares*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, pp. 655–690.
- Chiu, Y.T., Zhu, Y.Q., Corbett, J., 2021. In the hearts and minds of employees: a model of pre-adoptive appraisal toward artificial intelligence in organizations. *Int. J. Inf. Manag.* 60, 102379.
- Choi, H., Kandampully, J., 2019. The effect of atmosphere on customer engagement in upscale hotels: an application of SOR paradigm. *Int. J. Hospit. Manag.* 77, 40–50.
- Chung, T.Y., Chen, Y.L., 2018. Exchanging social support on online teacher groups: relation to teacher self-efficacy. *Telematics Inf.* 35 (5), 1542–1552.
- Cohen, S., Wills, T.A., 1985. Stress, social support, and the buffering hypothesis. *Psychol. Bull.* 98 (2), 310.
- Crittenden, A.B., Crittenden, V.L., Crittenden, W.F., 2019. The digitalization triumvirate: how incumbents survive. *Bus. Horiz.* 62 (2), 259–266.
- Danczkerts, S., Kenning, P., 2019. "It's MY Service, it's MY Music": the role of psychological ownership in music streaming consumption. *Psychol. Market.* 36 (9), 803–816.
- Davis, F.D., 1989. Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Q.* 13 (3), 319–339.
- De Silva, M., Wang, P., Kuah, A.T., 2021. Why wouldn't green appeal drive purchase intention? Moderation effects of consumption values in the UK and China. *J. Bus. Res.* 122, 713–724.
- Dwivedi, Y.K., Hughes, L., Ismagilova, E., Aarts, G., Coombs, C., Crick, T., Duan, Y., Dwivedi, R., Edwards, J., Eirug, A., Galanos, V., 2019. Artificial intelligence (AI): multidisciplinary perspectives on emerging challenges, opportunities, and agenda for research, practice and policy. *Int. J. Inf. Manag.* 57, 101994. In press.
- Elliott, S.W., 2018. Artificial intelligence, robots, and work: is this time different? *Issues Sci. Technol.* 35 (1), 40–44.
- Finn, A., 2012. Customer delight: distinct construct or zone of nonlinear response to customer satisfaction? *J. Serv. Res.* 15 (1), 99–110.
- Flavián, C., Pérez-Rueda, A., Belanche, D., Casaló, L.V., 2022. Intention to use analytical artificial intelligence (AI) in services – the effect of technology readiness and awareness. *J. Serv. Manag.* 33 (2), 293–320.
- Fornell, C., Larcker, D.F., 1981. Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error. *J. Market. Res.* 18 (1), 39–50.
- Gan, C., 2017. Understanding WeChat users' liking behavior: an empirical study in China. *Comput. Hum. Behav.* 68, 30–39.
- Gaustad, T., Samuelsen, B.M., Warlop, L., Fitzsimons, G.J., 2018. The perils of self-brand connections: consumer response to changes in brand meaning. *Psychol. Market.* 35 (11), 818–829.
- Grewal, D., Roggeveen, A.L., Nordfält, J., 2017. The future of retailing. *J. Retailing* 93 (1), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretai.2016.12.008>.
- Habibi, M.R., Laroche, M., Richard, M.O., 2014. The roles of brand community and customer engagement in building brand trust on social media. *Comput. Hum. Behav.* 37, 152–161.
- Hair, J.F., Ringle, C.M., Sarstedt, M., 2012. Partial least squares: the better approach to structural equation modeling? *Long. Range Plan.* 45 (5–6), 312–319.
- Hasan, R., Thaichon, P., Weaven, S., 2021. Are we already living with skynet? Anthropomorphic artificial intelligence to enhance customer experience. In: Thaichon, P., Ratten, V. (Eds.), *Developing Digital Marketing*. Emerald Publishing Limited, Bingley, pp. 103–134.
- Henseler, J., Chin, W.W., 2010. A comparison of approaches for the analysis of interaction effects between latent variables using partial least squares path modeling. *Struct. Equ. Model.* 17 (1), 82–109.
- Hicks, A., Comp, S., Horowitz, J., Hovarter, M., Miki, M., Bevan, J.L., 2012. Why people use Yelp. Com: an exploration of uses and gratifications. *Comput. Hum. Behav.* 28 (6), 2274–2279.
- Hsiao, K.L., Chen, C.C., 2016. What drives in-app purchase intention for mobile games? An examination of perceived values and loyalty. *Electron. Commer. Res. Appl.* 16, 18–29.
- Huang, K.-Y., Nambisan, P., Uzuner, Ö., 2010. Informational support or emotional support: preliminary study of an automated approach to analyze online support community contents. *ICIS 2010 Proceedings* 1–11.
- Jamieson, P., Fisher, K., Gilding, T., Taylor, P.G., Trevitt, A.C.F., 2000. Place and space in the design of new learning environments. *High Educ. Res. Dev.* 19 (2), 221–236.
- Jang, M., Jung, Y., Kim, S., 2021. Investigating managers' understanding of chatbots in the Korean financial industry. *Comput. Hum. Behav.* 120, 106747 in press.

- Kao, T.Y., Yang, M.H., Wu, J.T.B., Cheng, Y.Y., 2016. Co-creating value with consumers through social media. *J. Serv. Market.* 30 (2), 141–151.
- Khamis, S., Ang, L., Welling, R., 2016. Self-branding, 'micro-celebrity' and the rise of social media influencers. *Celebr. Stud.* 8 (2), 191–208.
- Kim, H.K., Kim, W.K., 2017. An exploratory study for artificial intelligence shopping information service. *J. Distrib. Sci.* 15 (4), 69–78.
- Kumar, V., Rajan, B., Venkatesan, R., Lecinski, J., 2019. Understanding the role of artificial intelligence in personalized engagement marketing. *Calif. Manag. Rev.* 61 (4), 135–155.
- Laroche, M., Habibi, M.R., Richard, M.O., Sankaranarayanan, R., 2012. The effects of social media based brand communities on brand community markers, value creation practices, brand trust and brand loyalty. *Comput. Hum. Behav.* 28 (5), 1755–1767.
- Lee, C.T., Pan, L.Y., Hsieh, S.H., 2022. Artificial intelligent chatbots as brand promoters: a two-stage structural equation modeling-artificial neural network approach. *Internet Res.* 32 (4), 1329–1356.
- Leong, L.Y., Hew, T.S., Ooi, K.B., Wei, J., 2020. Predicting mobile wallet resistance: a two-staged structural equation modeling-artificial neural network approach. *Int. J. Inf. Manag.* 51, 102047.
- Leong, L.Y., Jaafar, N.I., Ainin, S., 2018. Understanding Facebook commerce (f-commerce) actual purchase from an artificial neural network perspective. *J. Electron. Commer. Res.* 19 (1).
- Liang, Y., Lee, S.H., Workman, J.E., 2020. Implementation of artificial intelligence in fashion: are consumers ready? *Cloth. Text. Res. J.* 38 (1), 3–18.
- Lin, C., Lekhawipat, W., 2014. Factors affecting online repurchase intention. *Ind. Manag. Data Syst.* 114 (4), 597–611.
- Little, R.J.A., 1988. Missing-data adjustments in large surveys. *J. Bus. Econ. Stat.* 6 (3), 287–296.
- Liu, L., Lee, M.K., Liu, R., Chen, J., 2018. Trust transfer in social media brand communities: the role of consumer engagement. *Int. J. Inf. Manag.* 41, 1–13.
- Liu, X., Wang, Y., Liu, Y., 2019. The mediating effect of perceived value between product information push and consumer purchase behavior – multiple intermediary analysis based on bootstrap method. *Mod. Bus* 9 (1), 41–43.
- Loureiro, S.M.C., Gorgus, T., Kaufmann, H.R., 2017. Antecedents and outcomes of online brand engagement: the role of brand love on enhancing electronic-word-of-mouth. *Online Inf. Rev.* 41 (7), 985–1005.
- Lu, X., Que, D., Cao, G., 2016. Volatility forecast based on the hybrid artificial neural network and GARCH-type models. *Procedia Comput. Sci.* 91, 1044–1049.
- Majeed, M., Asare, C., Fatawu, A., Abubakari, A., 2022. An analysis of the effects of customer satisfaction and engagement on social media on repurchase intention in the hospitality industry. *Cogent Business & Management* 9 (1), 2028331.
- Mehrabian, A., Russell, J.A., 1974. The basic emotional impact of environments. *Percept. Mot. Skills* 38 (1), 283–301.
- Mogaji, E., Soetan, T.O., Kieu, T.A., 2020. The implications of artificial intelligence on the digital marketing of financial services to vulnerable customers. *Australasian Marketing Journal j-ausmj* 29 (3), 235–243. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ausmj.2020.05.003>.
- Moon, S., Jalali, N., Erevelles, S., 2021. Segmentation of both reviewers and businesses on social media. *J. Retailing Consum. Serv.* 61, 102524.
- Nadeem, W., Tan, T.M., Tajvidi, M., Hajli, N., 2021. How do experiences enhance brand relationship performance and value co-creation in social commerce? The role of consumer engagement and self-brand-connection. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Change* 171, 120952.
- Oghuma, A.P., Libaque-Saenz, C.F., Wong, S.F., Chang, Y., 2016. An expectation-confirmation model of continuance intention to use mobile instant messaging. *Telematics Inf.* 33 (1), 34–47.
- Overgoor, G., Chica, M., Rand, W., Weishampel, A., 2019. Letting the computers take over: using AI to solve marketing problems. *Calif. Manag. Rev.* 61 (4), 156–185.
- Pandita, S., Mishra, H.G., Chib, S., 2021. Psychological impact of covid-19 crises on students through the lens of Stimulus-Organism-Response (SOR) model. *Child. Youth Serv. Rev.* 120, 105783.
- Pantano, E., Giglio, S., Dennis, C., 2019. Making sense of consumers' tweets: sentiment outcomes for fast fashion retailers through Big Data analytics. *Int. J. Retail Distrib. Manag.* 47 (9), 915–927.
- Paschen, J., Wilson, M., Ferreira, J.J., 2020. Collaborative intelligence: how human and artificial intelligence create value along the B2B sales funnel. *Bus. Horiz.* 63 (3), 403–414.
- Pillai, R., Sivathanu, B., Dwivedi, Y.K., 2020. Shopping intention at AI-powered automated retail stores (AIPARS). *J. Retailing Consum. Serv.* 57, 102207.
- Podsakoff, P.M., MacKenzie, S.B., Lee, J.Y., Podsakoff, N.P., 2003. Common method biases in behavioral research: a critical review of the literature and recommended remedies. *J. Appl. Psychol.* 88 (5), 879.
- Potdar, V., Joshi, S., Harish, R., Baskerville, R., Wong thongtham, P., 2018. A process model for identifying online customer engagement patterns on Facebook brand. *Inf. Technol. People* 31 (2), 595–614.
- Rather, R.A., 2021. Monitoring the impacts of tourism-based social media, risk perception and fear on tourist's attitude and revisiting behaviour in the wake of COVID-19 pandemic. *Curr. Issues Tourism* 24 (23), 3275–3283.
- Reinartz, W., Wiegand, N., Imschloss, M., 2019. The impact of digital transformation on the retailing value chain. *Int. J. Res. Market.* 36 (3), 350–366.
- Rezaei, S., Ghodsi, S.S., 2014. Does value matters in playing online game? An empirical study among massively multiplayer online role-playing games (MMORPGS). *Comput. Hum. Behav.* 35, 252–266.
- Ringle, C.M., Wende, S., Will, A., 2005. "Smartpls 2.0" available at: www.smartpls.de.
- Rioux, L., Scrima, F., Werner, C.M., 2017. Space appropriation and place attachment: University students create places. *J. Environ. Psychol.* 50, 60–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2017.02.003>.
- Rozzell, B., Piercy, C.W., Carr, C.T., King, S., Lane, B.L., Tornes, M., Wright, K.B., 2014. Notification pending: online social support from close and nonclose relational ties via Facebook. *Comput. Hum. Behav.* 38, 272–280.
- Rubin, D.B., 1987. Multiple Imputation for Nonresponse in Surveys. John Wiley & Sons, New York.
- Samara, D., Magnisalis, I., Peristeras, V., 2020. Artificial intelligence and big data in tourism: a systematic literature review. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology* 11 (2), 343–367.
- Sands, S., Ferraro, C., Campbell, C., Tsao, H.Y., 2021. Managing the human-chatbot divide: how service scripts influence service experience. *J. Serv. Manag.* 32 (2), 246–264.
- Sarkar, S., Chauhan, S., Khare, A., 2020. A meta-analysis of antecedents and consequences of trust in mobile commerce. *Int. J. Inf. Manag.* 50, 286–301.
- Satti, Z.W., Babar, S.F., Parveen, S., Abrar, K., Shabbir, A., 2020. Innovations for potential entrepreneurs in service quality and customer loyalty in the hospitality industry. *Asia pacific journal of innovation and entrepreneurship* 14 (3), 317–328.
- Schafer, J.L., Olsen, M.K., 1998. Multiple imputation for multivariate missing-data problems: a data analyst's perspective. *Multivariate Behav. Res.* 33 (4), 545–571.
- Sharma, N., Singh, V.K., 2016. Effect of workplace incivility on job satisfaction and turnover intentions in India. *S. Asian J. Global Bus. Res.* 5 (2), 234–249.
- Sharma, S., Khadka, A., 2019. Role of empowerment and sense of community on online social health support group. *Inf. Technol. People* 32 (6), 1564–1590.
- Singh, N., Sinha, N., Liébana-Cabanillas, F.J., 2020. Determining factors in the adoption and recommendation of mobile wallet services in India: analysis of the effect of innovativeness, stress to use and social influence. *Int. J. Inf. Manag.* 50, 191–205.
- Sohn, K., Kwon, O., 2020. Technology acceptance theories and factors influencing artificial intelligence-based intelligent products. *Telematics Inf.* 47 (1), 101324.
- Song, J., Wang, H., Liu, Y., Wu, W., Dai, G., Wu, Z., Deng, K., 2020. End-to-end automatic differentiation of the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) from viral pneumonia based on chest CT. *Eur. J. Nucl. Med. Mol. Imag.* 47, 2516–2524.
- Su, L., Swanson, S.R., Chinchanchokchai, S., Hsu, M.K., Chen, X., 2016. Reputation and intentions: the role of satisfaction, identification, and commitment. *J. Bus. Res.* 69 (9), 3261–3269.
- Tan, C.W., Benbasat, I., Cenfetelli, R.T., 2013. IT-mediated customer service content and delivery in electronic governments: an empirical service quality. *MIS Q.* 37 (1), 77–109.
- Thakur, R., 2018. Customer engagement and online reviews. *J. Retailing Consum. Serv.* 41, 48–59.
- Torres, P., Augusto, M., Matos, M., 2019. Antecedents and outcomes of digital influencer endorsement: an exploratory study. *Psychol. Market.* 36 (12), 1267–1276.
- Upadhyay, N., Kamble, A., 2023. Examining Indian consumer pro-environment purchase intention of electric vehicles: perspective of stimulus-organism-response. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Change* 189, 122344.
- Wang, P., Huang, Q., Davison, R.M., 2020. How Do Digital Influencers Affect Social Commerce Intention? the Roles of Social Power and Satisfaction. *Information Technology and People*.
- Weber, F., Schütte, R., 2019. A domain-oriented analysis of the impact of machine learning – the case of retailing. *Big Data and Cognitive Computing* 3 (1), 11.
- Wen, C.-H., Cheng, C.-C., Shih, Y.-C., 2022. Artificial intelligence technologies for more flexible recommendation in uniforms. *Data Technol. Appl.* 56 (4), 626–643.
- Xu, Y., Zhang, W., Bao, H., Zhang, S., Xiang, Y., 2019. A SEM-neural network approach to predict customers' intention to purchase battery electric vehicles in China's Zhejiang province. *Sustainability* 11 (11), 3164.
- Yang, H.C., DeHart, J.L., 2016. Social media use and online political participation among college students during the US election 2012. *Social Media Society* 2 (1), 2056305115623802.
- Yang, L., Henthorne, T.L., George, B., 2020. Artificial intelligence and robotics technology in the hospitality industry: current applications and future trends. *Digital transformation in business and society: Theory and cases* 211–228.
- Yin, J., Qiu, X., 2021. AI technology and online purchase intention: structural equation model based on perceived value. *Sustainability* 13 (10), 5671.
- Yuksel, A., Yuksel, F., Bilim, Y., 2010. Destination attachment: effects on customer satisfaction and cognitive, affective and conative loyalty. *Tourism Manag.* 31 (2), 274–284.
- Zhou, F., Chu, Z., Sun, H., Hu, R.Q., Hanzo, L., 2018. Artificial noise aided secure cognitive beamforming for cooperative MISO-NOMA using SWIPT. *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, 36 (4), 918–931.
- Zhu, Y., Janssen, M., Wang, R., Liu, Y., 2022. It is me, chatbot: working to address the COVID-19 outbreak-related mental health issues in China. User experience, satisfaction, and influencing factors. *Int. J. Hum. Comput. Interact.* 38 (12), 1182–1194.
- Zhu, Y., Zhang, R., Zou, Y., Jin, D., 2023. Investigating customers' responses to artificial intelligence chatbots in online travel agencies: the moderating role of product familiarity. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology* 14 (2), 208–224.